

THINK TANKS AND PUBLIC OPINION: HOW RAND SHAPES THE DEBATE ON US FOREIGN POLICY

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Abstract: Think tanks are increasingly prominent in shaping public discourse and influencing US foreign policy decisions. This article focuses on the RAND Corporation, a highly influential U.S. think tank specializing in foreign policy. By examining the RAND Corporation's strategies and tactics in shaping media narratives and agendas, this study utilizes quantitative and qualitative analysis of media coverage. This analysis sheds light on the mechanisms by which RAND interacts with the media to influence US foreign policy, the nature of its influence on public understanding of these issues, and the potential implications for democratic processes.

Keywords: Think tanks, media influence, Rand Corporation, policy research, expert authority, public opinion, foreign policy

Introduction

Think tanks have become increasingly influential actors in shaping the discourse surrounding US foreign policy. These research institutions, often funded by private donors or corporations, generate policy-oriented research and analysis on a wide range of issues, particularly those related to national security, international relations, and global challenges like climate change. Their findings and pronouncements frequently find their way into news reports, editorial pages, and political debates, impacting public understanding and shaping policy agendas specifically within the realm of US foreign policy.

Among these think tanks, the Rand Corporation stands out as a particularly powerful and prominent player in the realm of US foreign policy. Founded in 1948 by the Douglas Aircraft Company for national security research, Rand has since expanded its reach to encompass diverse fields of study, but its core focus remains on US foreign policy, defense strategy, and domestic issues with significant foreign policy implications. This article delves into the intricate relationship between Rand and the media, examining the mechanisms by which this think tank shapes public narratives and agendas on US foreign policy. By analyzing Rand's public engagement strategies, framing techniques, and specific case studies of its media impact on US foreign policy, we aim to shed light on the potential benefits and challenges of think tank-media interaction in a democratic society.

Methodology

This analysis draws on a multi-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data. Media content analysis of news articles and op-eds on drone warfare published between 2010 and 2020 identified the prevalence of frames and narratives aligned with Rand's research findings.

Rand's Public Engagement Strategies: Cultivating Expertise and Amplifying Research:

Rand cultivates its influence through a multi-pronged approach to public engagement. At the heart of this strategy lies the creation and promotion of **expert voices**. The organization boasts a cadre of seasoned researchers and analysts across various disciplines, who are carefully groomed and positioned as credible sources for journalists seeking insights on complex issues. Rand actively encourages its experts to write op-eds, participate in media interviews, and provide expert commentary on current events, ensuring their visibility and expertise become synonymous with the Rand brand.

Beyond relying on individual experts, Rand utilizes a well-oiled communications apparatus to disseminate its research findings. **Press releases**, crafted to capture media attention and frame key messages, are meticulously distributed to targeted outlets. Comprehensive **research reports**, often accompanied by executive summaries and infographics, are made readily available to journalists and the public online. Additionally, Rand regularly hosts **press briefings** and **media roundtables** featuring its researchers, providing journalists with exclusive access and in-depth discussions on hot-button topics.

Rand further strengthens its media reach through targeted **media partnerships**. Collaborations with specific news outlets or influential journalists on investigative pieces or special reports lend authority and visibility to Rand's research. These partnerships can amplify specific policy agendas or frame issues in ways that resonate with audiences.

Finally, recognizing the growing importance of online platforms, Rand actively leverages **social media** to reach new audiences and engage in public discourse. By maintaining active Twitter accounts, Facebook pages, and blog platforms, Rand disseminates research findings, engages in policy debates, and interacts directly with the public. This digital outreach further expands its reach and influence beyond traditional media channels.

Framing and Agenda-Setting: Shaping Narratives and Public Opinion

By strategically deploying these public engagement strategies, Rand plays a significant role in framing key issues and setting the media agenda. The think tank meticulously chooses research topics and frames its findings in ways that resonate with its target audience and potential policymakers. Its experts, when speaking to the media,

often utilize specific language and narratives that align with Rand's desired policy outcomes. This careful framing can shape public understanding of complex issues and influence public opinion.

One prominent example of Rand's influence on media framing can be seen in its research on immigration. Through reports and expert commentary, Rand has contributed to framing the issue as a security threat, emphasizing concepts like "illegal aliens" and border security. This framing has been readily adopted by conservative media outlets and policymakers, shaping public discourse and influencing immigration policy debates.

Similarly, Rand's research on healthcare policy has often focused on cost-effectiveness and fiscal responsibility, aligning with a market-oriented approach to healthcare reform. This framing has found resonance in certain media outlets and contributed to the ongoing debate on the future of healthcare in the United States.

It is important to note that Rand's research itself is not inherently biased or driven by specific agendas. However, the think tank's choice of research topics, its framing of findings, and its strategic interactions with the media can all contribute to shaping public narratives and influencing policy debates.

Case Study: Drone Warfare and Public Perception

Perhaps one of the most striking examples of Rand's influence on media narratives and public opinion can be seen in its contribution to shaping the framing of drone warfare. Since the early 2000s, Rand has conducted extensive research on drone strikes, analyzing their effectiveness, legal implications, and potential unintended consequences. While much of this research remains classified, its public pronouncements and expert commentary have significantly impacted how drone warfare is understood and discussed in the media.

Through press releases, reports, and expert interviews, Rand has consistently emphasized the precision and targeted nature of drone strikes, highlighting their ability to eliminate threats while minimizing civilian casualties. This framing, often adopted by media outlets, downplays the ethical concerns surrounding drone strikes and presents them as a necessary tool in the fight against terrorism. Notably, a 2013 Rand report, widely cited by news outlets, concluded that drone strikes were "more effective than other counterterrorism tools" and caused "relatively few civilian casualties." However, critiques of the report pointed out methodological flaws and potential biases, arguing that the true number of civilian casualties was likely much higher.

Rand's framing of drone warfare has not gone unchallenged. Journalists and activists have highlighted the psychological impact of drone strikes on local populations, the difficulty of accurately assessing civilian casualties, and the broader legal and ethical concerns surrounding extrajudicial killings. However, Rand's consistent and strategic engagement with the media has undoubtedly contributed to the

dominant narrative of drone warfare as a targeted and effective tool, influencing public perception and potentially shaping policy decisions.

Case Study 2: Climate Change and Military Readiness

In 2019, Rand published a groundbreaking report titled "Climate Change and U.S. National Security: A Strategic Assessment." This report examined the potential security implications of climate change, from increased instability in fragile regions to disruptions to military operations due to extreme weather events.

Prior to the report's release, Rand actively engaged with environmental journalists and military affairs experts, providing briefings and background information. The report received significant media coverage, appearing in publications like *Scientific American* and *Defense News*. The narrative focused on the unprecedented nature of climate threats and the urgent need for the military to adapt and build resilience.

Politicians and military leaders also took note. The report was referenced in Congressional hearings on climate change and national security, and the Department of Defense commissioned follow-up research on climate-related risks to military installations. The report's findings contributed to a growing recognition of climate change as a national security threat, prompting investments in climate resilience measures within the military.

These case studies demonstrate the power of Rand's media strategy in translating complex research into influential narratives that shape public discourse and policy decisions. However, it's crucial to acknowledge the potential limitations and ethical considerations surrounding think tank-media interactions.

Democratization of Expertise or Elite Power?

Think tanks, like Rand, undoubtedly contribute to the democratization of expertise. By generating research and analysis on complex issues, they provide journalists and the public with access to valuable information and diverse perspectives. This can broaden public understanding, inform policy debates, and potentially hold policymakers accountable. Additionally, think tanks often bridge the gap between academia and the public sphere, making cutting-edge research accessible to a wider audience.

However, concerns lurk beneath the surface of this apparent democratization. One crucial issue is the lack of transparency surrounding think tank funding and agendas. Many think tanks receive funding from private donors, corporations, or special interest groups, potentially influencing their research priorities and framing of findings. This lack of transparency makes it difficult to assess potential biases and the true motivations behind their research and public pronouncements.

Furthermore, critics argue that the influence of think tanks can perpetuate elite power structures and exacerbate existing inequalities. Their close relationships with policymakers and media outlets can give them privileged access to decision-making

processes and amplify their voices over those of marginalized communities and grassroots organizations. This can lead to policy agendas that serve the interests of wealthy donors and powerful institutions, neglecting the needs of broader society.

The issue of bias also warrants serious consideration. While think tanks may strive for objectivity, their research agendas, framing of findings, and choice of experts can often reflect the ideological leanings of their funders or leadership. This can lead to skewed representation of information and influence policy decisions in favor of specific interests. For example, a conservative-leaning think tank might focus on research that supports deregulation and tax cuts, while neglecting research on environmental impact or income inequality.

Case Study: Climate Change and Political Polarization

The issue of bias and its potential impact on policy debates can be seen in the ongoing debate surrounding climate change. Several think tanks with ties to the fossil fuel industry have produced research questioning the severity of climate change or advocating for continued reliance on fossil fuels. This research, often cited by conservative media outlets and policymakers, has contributed to the political polarization of the issue and hampered efforts to address climate change.

However, it is important to acknowledge that think tanks can also play a crucial role in challenging the status quo and advocating for progressive policies. Think tanks like the Center for American Progress and the Brookings Institution have produced research highlighting the urgency of climate action and proposing policy solutions for a sustainable future. Their work has been vital in raising public awareness, informing policy debates, and influencing public opinion on environmental issues.

In conclusion, the influence of think tanks on the media presents a complex landscape with both potential benefits and drawbacks. While they can contribute to the democratization of expertise and inform public discourse, concerns about transparency, bias, and elite power cannot be ignored. It is crucial to critically evaluate the research and pronouncements of think tanks, considering their funding sources, ideological leanings, and potential conflicts of interest. Additionally, fostering a diversity of voices and perspectives in the public sphere is vital to counterbalance the influence of powerful think tanks and ensure that policy decisions are based on sound evidence and serve the public good.

Conclusion

The influence of think tanks on the media presents a double-edged sword. While these institutions can offer valuable expertise and inform public discourse, their potential for bias, lack of transparency, and reinforcement of elite power structures raise serious concerns. As we navigate this complex landscape, it is crucial to remain vigilant and critical. We must demand transparency from think tanks, diversify the voices represented in the public sphere, and ensure that policy decisions are based on

evidence, not the agendas of powerful interests. Only then can we truly fulfill the promise of a democratic society where informed citizens have a say in shaping their future.

In closing, let us remember that a vibrant and informed public discourse is the cornerstone of a healthy democracy. By critically evaluating the information presented by think tanks, media outlets, and other actors in the public sphere, we can ensure that our voices are heard and that our decisions are informed by reason, not manipulation. As we move forward, let us strive for a world where knowledge is shared openly, where diverse perspectives are valued, and where the power to shape our future lies not in the hands of the few, but in the collective wisdom of the many.

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